

Study of thermal behavior and PL properties of Yb₂O₃-Al₂O₃ glass microspheres

A. Prnová^{1,2}, A. Plško², J. Valúchová^{1,2}, R. Klement², M. Majerová³, D. Galusek^{1,2}

¹*Institute of Inorganic Chemistry of Slovak Academy of Sciences, Bratislava, Dúbravská cesta 9, SK-845 36, Slovakia*

²*VILA – Joined Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, FChPT STU, Študentská 2, SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia*

³*Department of Magnetometry, Institute of Measurement Science, Slovak Academy of Sciences, Dúbravská cesta 9, 841 04 Bratislava, Slovak Republic*

The ytterbium aluminium garnet composition (Yb₃Al₅O₁₂), YbA-G (62.5 mol.% Al₂O₃, 37.5 mol.% Yb₂O₃), was prepared in the form of glass microspheres by flame synthesis, using a methane-oxygen flame. To obtain a high homogeneity of glass microspheres, a modified sol-gel Pechini method [1] was used to prepare the starting powder. Only the presence of a wider hump in the interval 23-40° in 2-theta range was observed in the XRD pattern of the prepared glass microspheres, which indicates the predominantly amorphous nature of the sample. However, the next detailed study on the morphology of the prepared system by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) showed the presence of a small portion of partially, or fully, crystallised microspheres (Fig. 1). The high-temperature X-ray powder diffraction analysis (HT XRD) was carried out in the temperature interval of 750-1450°C, and with a step size of 5°C, to determine the temperature influence on the phase composition. Only the crystallisation of Yb₃Al₅O₁₂, a ytterbium aluminium garnet phase (COD-04-001-9735), was observed throughout the temperature range. The DSC analyses, with heating rates of 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10°C/min, in the temperature interval of 25-1200°C, were performed in a N₂ atmosphere to better understand the temperature behaviour of the prepared glass microspheres. Two exothermic effects at 910°C and 933°C were observed, which can be attributed to the crystallisation of Yb₃Al₅O₁₂. The crystallization kinetics of the prepared sample were examined in terms of the JMAK model and the kinetic triplet (frequency factor \underline{A} , apparent activation energy \underline{E}_{app} , and the Avrami coefficient \underline{m}) was determined (Tab. 1) using RSS, R²_{adj}, and AIC criteria. Finally, the PL spectra was measured and results were compared with results of our previous work and discussed.

Fig. 1 SEM analysis a) prepared YbA-G sample, b) detail of crystallized microsphere

Tab. 1 The determined kinetic triplets

Peak	m	A ± sd [min ⁻¹]	E _{app} ± sd [kJ.mol ⁻¹]
1	3	(1.76±2.0)10 ²⁸	(6.39±0.08)10 ⁵
2	2	(1.28±1.6)10 ⁵⁵	(1.27±0.09)10 ⁶

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References

- [1] M. P. Pechini, "Method of Preparing Lead and Alkaline-Earth Titanates and Niobates and Coating Method Using the Same to Form a Capacitor," U.S. Pat. No. 3330697, July 11, 1967
- [2] A. Prnová, K. Bodišová, R. Klement, M. Migát, P. Veteška, M. Škrátek, E. Bruneel, I. Van Driessche, D. Galusek, Preparation and characterization of $\text{Yb}_2\text{O}_3 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ glasses by the Pechini sol – gel method combined with flame synthesis, 40 (2014) 6179–6184.
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